

Enhancing Cooperation Between LEAs and Citizens using Social Networks - the INSPEC²T Approach

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Introduction

Enhancing the feeling of public safety and crime prevention are tasks customarily assigned to the Police. Police departments have, however, recognized that traditional ways of policing methods are becoming obsolete; Community Policing (CP) philosophy, however when applied appropriately, leads to seamless collaboration between various stakeholders like the Police, NGOs and the General Public and provides the opportunity to identify risks, assist in solving problems related to crime, disorder, safety and crucially contributes to improving the quality of life for everyone in a community.

As an enabler to the above, Social Media, due to its high level of infiltration in modern life, constitutes a powerful mechanism which offers additional and direct communication channels for reaching individuals or communities. When the feedback gained via these channels is taken into account by Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) in a structured and coordinated manner, these channels can be utilized to improve the citizens' perception of the Police and to capture individual and community needs.

This article presents research conducted under INSPEC²T (Inspiring CItizeNS Participation for Enhanced Community PoliCing ActIons)¹, a project funded by the European Commission's research agenda to bridge the gap between CP as a philosophy and as an organizational strategy, capitalizing on the use of Social Media. The project aims to increase transparency, trust, police accountability, and the role of civil society. It aspires to build strong, trusting relationships between LEAs (Law Enforcement Agencies) and the public, supporting two-way, contemporary communication while at the same time respecting anonymity of all affected parties.

Requirements for an advanced CP solution

End user needs

The INSEPC²T consortium began the 3-year project in May 2015 by reviewing the existing research literature, so as to design the online surveys regarding the end user requirements. Four online surveys in total were conducted, aimed at the following CP stakeholders: i) European citizens, ii) Neighbourhood watch associations and NGOs/Societal Workers with focus on CP, iii) Police academia, and iv) LEAs assigned with CP tasks.

The first survey launched was aimed at users from the 'general public'. Citizens across European countries are considered potential users of the INSPEC²T platform, so it was imperative to capture their needs and wants and understand the reasons behind them. A second survey was aimed at NGOs, community workers, city administrators and other actors who either professionally or on a voluntary basis are involved with security and safety in communities. The participants were asked to provide their experiences about CP and the use of Social Media. The third and fourth survey sought to capture the views of police colleges /

¹ http://cordis.europa.eu/result/rcn/195176_en.html

universities / academies involved in the training of police students, and active CP practitioners from EU member states.

The surveys remained open and accessible for 6 months (between August 2015 and January 2016) and was disseminated via Social Media. Respondents were mainly from England, Northern Ireland, the Netherlands, Germany, Spain, Greece and Cyprus. It should be noted that countries with mature CP programs (e.g. England, Northern Ireland, Netherlands, Spain), and countries where CP schemes are not so widely engulfed in the broader Police strategic planning (e.g. Greece, Cyprus) contributed.

Further to the online surveys, focus group discussions and interviews were also conducted. The participants were selected from two distinct groups. 1) The “official” CP practitioners which are LEAs assigned with CP tasks and received appropriate training and 2) the General Public, consisting of citizens with diverse backgrounds who may or may not have been accustomed to CP terms and applications. The interviews were structured to capture experience, lessons learned, best practices and also record suggestions. The focus group discussions took place in Greece, the UK, Cyprus, the Netherlands and Spain.

In addition to the online surveys and the focus groups, INSPEC²T utilised a Stakeholder Advisory Group (SAG) and an External Expert Group (EEG). These committees are made up of LEAs, government representatives, active citizen groups, community organizations, commercial associations, and CP visionaries. EEG members are distinguished Academics in Policing, Data Protection and subject matter experts in EU Ethical and Legal frameworks. The advisory committees, external to the project, were presented with the analysis of more than 2,000 responses from online surveys and focus group interviews which were used to define the functionalities and system specifications.

CP gap analysis

The above activities were performed in order to produce a gap analysis of the CP practices and associated technological tools which are currently in use. This allowed the INSPEC²T partners to elaborate on and consolidate the End User Requirements. The survey analysis² indicated a strong preference by Citizens to engage with the police using Social Media and modern communications means like email, mobile applications and websites. Following the citizens’ response about their preference to communicate with the police using modern technologies, the impact of Social Media was studied in detail with a series of questions such as: - Proactively address crime root causes in the community, - Improve the quality of life for everyone in the community, - Stimulate citizens’ own responsibilities in cooperating with the police, - Improve legitimacy of police operations within communities, - Build better relationships and trust between police and the community as a whole.

One of the key outcomes of the surveys, as well as discussions conducted, is that more than three out of four citizens believe that modernizing the ways they communicate with the police will proactively address crime root causes in the community, will improve the quality of life, will stimulate citizens to cooperate with the police and will improve legitimacy of police operations within the community. Therefore, a CP program based on Social Media is an opportunity to improve the relationship between the general public and the police.

² D1.2 - End User Requirements - 1st SAG Report available online at <http://inspec2t-project.eu/en/public-deliverables>

The INSPEC²T approach to enhance LEA and community cooperation

Nowadays, the rise of virtual communities and social networks have complicated the relationships with police who are organised geographically and hierarchically. Against the background of cultural and ethnic diversity, the spread of new technologies injects an element of homogeneity and of a seemingly level playing field. Therefore, the implementation of social media components should be exploited by the police to interact with all members of a community.

Differences have to be taken into account with regard to language, technology, relations between the citizenry and the police as well as cultural understandings of crime, police, law and order. As surveys pointed out, a modernised CP approach shall embrace the use of a fully functional mobile social media interactive system. The new Social Media system should enable direct communication and collaboration with community members in real time.

Police departments will use such a system to disseminate information to the public, as well as to obtain information, especially for tactical purposes, such as for gathering information about threats of mob violence, riots, or isolated criminal activity during otherwise-lawful mass demonstrations. Citizens, on the other hand, may be informed in real time about any incident in their neighbourhood, as well as report or give information back that may be of use to their local police department by a simple post, comment, photo, or video (captured by smart mobile devices). The whole concept builds on the bidirectional information flow, so as to promote participation, motivation and engagement of citizens and empower them to assist in their own public safety and security.

Of course, performing such operations via Social Media act as an extension to existing policing practices. As with existing practices, all police operations take place in an environment that is highly regulated and follows ethics and legislations. The framework that defines the relation between advanced CP operations with regulations of public media platforms must be set and utilised. Therefore, the development of the INSPEC²T (or any other similar) system has to ensure that all applications and usage of the system is compliant with related national and EU legislation in force.

The INSPEC²T concept and developed solution

INSPEC²T aspires to develop a sustainable framework for CP that effectively addresses and promotes seamless collaboration between the police and various communities and is based both on an EU crime prevention paradigm and Member States' Specific Internal Security Policies.

Fig.1. The INSPEC²T Concept

The concept visualised in **Fig.1.** supports incident reporting from registered and anonymous community members using a social media network. The reports are processed by an intelligent system, which supports bidirectional and personalized communications, engages community members to provide additional information and better utilises police resources.

INSPEC²T Solution Modules

An advanced CP solution should possess intelligent functionalities and the overall architecture should be modular and should be based on open standard interfaces. As such, existing analysis modules and databases will be utilized and will be part of the advanced CP ecosystem. The intelligence made available by the INSPEC²T approach is based on the following modules: Reporting tools, awareness raising & serious games and intelligent command & control modules.

Mobile Applications (Mob App) and Public Portal (PP)

Two different incident reporting functionalities are supported. Citizens can either submit reports to the Public Portal using a computer or smartphone (without the installation of any application), or by installing the INSPEC²T mobile application on their smartphones/tablets (Fig.2). An extended (in terms of functionalities) version of the mobile application is available to CP officers for managing the reports and for further interacting with the system and its operators. Apart of the mobile application and the Public Portal, an awareness game is also available. The game (Resource Force³) aims to raise awareness about the citizens' contribution-value to CP. The citizens have the options to submit reports anonymously, or as registered users, within the system and to engage further with the police and their community.

Geospatial Complex Event Processing (GCEP)

The challenge of processing huge amounts of spatial data generated by either registered or anonymous users should be embedded. Although there are several ways to obtain location data about a reported incident, (GPS sensors, cellular positioning techniques), the provided datasets

³ <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.playgen.ResourceForce>

have real value when they are processed and analysed in a structural manner so as to generate meaningful information.

Fig.2. Screenshots of the Mobile Application for Citizens

Multimedia Analytics (MMA)

MMA should be capable of extracting semantic information from a wide range of multimedia data sources. Incident reports will contribute to increasing quantities of semi and unstructured data which represent various media objects such as: text, images, audio streams and videos. The MMA module should first process and then discard low quality data. The data of value should be analysed to extract speech transcription, acoustic event detection (e.g. identification of a gunshot), person/face detection and re-identification, as well as other multimedia correlations.

Business Intelligence Analytics (BIA)

BIA has the following responsibilities: (i) compute metrics for the activity and engagement of both citizens and police from all CP communication channels (e.g. community forums, social media accounts, etc.), (ii) implement sentiment analysis for the messages exchanged in the above-named channels, (iii) build a rating based user profile, by computing each user's activity within the advanced CP – Social Network, which characterizes how active the user is, if they are contributing helpful information to the system or if they are malicious. It has to be noted, however, that the rating essentially concerns the information provided by the user rather than the users themselves, (iv) compute user performance KPIs that will be used by other intelligence modules to encourage user participation in INSPEC²T. (v) classify the importance of each exchanged message, based on the author's profile ranking and other metrics and (vi) provide widgets that will visualize the above metrics.

Case Based Reasoning (CBR)

CBR is the process of solving new problems based on the solutions of similar past problems. In cases of uncertainty, or whenever decisions need to be taken based on different sources of information, this module will take action. The CBR module by design will consist of two different submodules. The first one will be composed of rules that the user could adjust or modify, allowing it to make use of expert knowledge. The second submodule will be equipped with a knowledge base and will allow the inference of new rules and actions based on previous

knowledge. In essence, the CBR module will deploy techniques allowing the implementation of a similarity measure between concepts and relations of the prevailing ontology.

Data Processing Ageing (DPA)

Ageing of data has to be configured according to the corresponding regulatory frameworks. Records may only be stored following a legitimate reason (massive storage of preventive data should not be allowed). Record lifetime and criteria for deletion have to be defined in accordance to Data protection legislation. The renewal of an item's date of expiration is possible and needs to be initiated from a user with the appropriate access rights. A mandatory description field justifying the need for this operation ensures that all data preservation actions are permanently retained for future reference and Ethical screening.

Fig.3. The INSPEC²T architecture

Data Warehouse (DWH)

DWH is integrating data from multiple heterogeneous sources and in different formats to support analytical reporting, structured and/or ad hoc queries and decision making. DWH is an architectural model designed to support the flow of data from operational modules to decision support systems. The large amounts of heterogeneous data provided by citizens and communities over time are arranged into abstracted subject areas with time-variant versions of the same records, with an appropriate level of data grain or detail to make it useful for the intelligent modules described above to retrieve and analyse them.

Secure Portal (SP)

The intelligence submodules mentioned above, (GCEP, MMA, BIA, CBR, DPA, and DWH) are all interfacing the Secure Portal (**Fig.4**). The SP is connected with the intelligence modules and present an advanced operational picture to its operators. The Law Enforcement Operator (LEO) and the INSPEC²T Supervisor Administrator are in control of all CP submitted reports and, by utilising the intelligent processing of the advanced CP system, they manage all the reported incidents.

Fig.4. View of the Secure Portal

Training Simulator

The training simulator module offers realistic in-situ simulations to allow the system administrators and Secure Portal operators to get familiarized with the platform, experience the potential impact of their decisions, interact in a safe environment, analyse their approach, facilitate peer assessment and benchmark so as to enable self-reflection and improvement. Moreover, the inclusion of courses with focus on privacy, data protection and how the system administrators can comply with ethical & legal and societal requirements should be mandatory items in an advanced CP training program.

Findings from the first three pilots

The first working INSPEC²T version first undertook trials in Belfast, in April 2017. CP Officers from Police Service Northern Ireland in cooperation with fellow Officers from Lancashire Constabulary participated, along with residents from the Holyland community and members of the Ulster University in the CP scenarios execution. The second pilot and a solution demo to SAG and EEG committees took place in Egkomi, Cyprus in May 2017. In Cyprus, the consortium conducted a series of small scale pilots and solution demonstrations which engaged municipalities and LEAs. The third pilot took place in Valencia, Spain. Further to the Valencia local police and local community involvement, there were police representatives from San Sebastian and Guardia Civil.

Fig.5. Left: Valencia, Bullying scenario execution in the city Centre, Center: Belfast, PSNI officer uses INSPEC²T mobile app for receiving CP notifications, Right: Egkomi: Debriefing of the SAG and EEG committees following a proof of concept demo.

The main scope of the first three pilots was twofold. One was to demonstrate and validate the strategic objectives of the project and then to present a working solution which satisfies the majority of end user requirements and requested functionalities, focusing on the everyday needs and problems of our end users; after all, INSPEC²T follows an end user driven approach. As such the empowerment of communities achieved through the facilitation and delivery of a more personalized service through which citizens collaborated with the police in setting their CP agenda, was tested and validated. To this extent, the delivered serious and awareness games and the training simulator were also demonstrated, tested and assessed. The output of the assessment will be used to provide further input to system developers.

The feedback from participants, (community members and associations, LEAs, CP visionaries) focuses on the following three areas:

1. Reporting interfaces - end users asked for more intuitive GUIs for the Mobile App for citizens and LEAs, and the Public Portal. If possible, the consortium should minimize the fields where text entry (typing) is required.
2. Backoffice components – (a) the following modules (MMA, GCEP, BIA, CBR, DWH, and the CAD interface that provides support to legacy incident reporting systems) should be integrated with existing police systems and (b) a light version of the Secure Portal should be planned for authorities responsible to act on reports like road deficiencies, illegal dumping and other non-police related issues.
3. There are a few concerns primarily from the LEA side about the data protection and the compliance of the submitted intelligence data with national and EU frameworks. However, it was acknowledged that police should adapt to modern social media challenges and modernize their response to crime and citizen complaints and follow a unified strategy for handling personal identification data

The way forward

As a conclusion, the element of enthusiasm which was demonstrated by participants during the pilots should be highlighted. Following the conclusion of the first three pilots, the consortium received requests for further testing in a variety of different CP contexts. The consortium members are currently working to evolve the features and add new functionalities prior to the second testing phase. The final system tests will take place in Groningen (Netherlands) between September and December 2017 and in Preston (UK) in November 2017.

Do you want to see the INSPEC²T solution Live Demo? Take part in the Next Generation Community Policing (NGCP) Conference! Learn more [here!](#)